

OntoFoCE and ObE Forensics. Email-traceability supporting tools for Digital Forensics
Parra, H., Vegetti, M.

Supplementary material: OntoFoCE CLASS DESCRIPTION

Below are the descriptions of classes and subclasses, relations, and axioms for each of the 14 classes defined in the OntoFoCE conceptual model.

ITEM	1	
CLASS	EMAIL	
SUBCLASSES		
SUBITEM	Subclass Name	Description
1.1	<i>FeasibleEmail</i>	An email that meets the feasibility requirements for its forensic analysis.
RELATIONS		
SUBITEM	Relationship Name	Description
1.2	<i>emailSentBySenderAccount</i>	It identifies the account that gives rise to the email, and it is required that the email has a single account that acts as a transmitter. Inverse of the relation 3.3
1.3	<i>emailHasOcurrence</i>	It links all the occurrences of the same email with the appropriate cardinality. It is the inverse of the relation 2.4
1.4	<i>emailReceivedByRecipientAccount</i>	It identifies the receiving account that receives the email, marking the appropriate cardinality. It is the inverse of the relation 3.5
1.5	<i>emailHasSequence</i>	It identifies the sequence corresponding to the email. It is the inverse of the relation 11.1
AXIOMS		
SUBITEM	Axiom in natural language	SWRL expression
1.6	<i>All Mail has a single Account that acts as a transmitter.</i>	<i>Email(?x), SenderAccount(?s1), SenderAccount(?s2), senderAccountSendsEmail (?s1, ?x), senderAccountSendsEmail (?s2, ?x) → SameAs (?s1, ?s2)</i>
	If the variable <i>?x</i> represents an instance of the <i>Email</i> class and <i>?s1, ?s2</i> represents instances of the <i>SenderAccount</i> that are linked to the email <i>?x</i> by the corresponding instances of the <i>senderAccountSendsEmail</i> (<i>senderAccountSendsEmail (?s1, ?x)</i> and <i>senderAccountSendsEmail (?s2, ?x)</i>) implies that <i>?s1</i> and <i>?s2</i> represent the same individual. The predicate <i>SameAs</i> (<i>?s1, ?s2</i>) is predefined in SWRL and evaluates true whether <i>?s1</i> and <i>?s2</i> are the same individual. If this predicate fails it implies that the email <i>?x</i> is linked to two accounts sender (<i>?s1</i> and <i>?s2</i>), a situation that is not valid in the domain.	
1.7	<i>An email is feasible to analyze when it has a header and it her contains the ip address of the sending device and the ip address of the receiving device.</i>	<i>Email(?x), Sequence(?s), emailHasSequence(?x, ?s), Thread(?t), sequenceHasThread(?s, ?t), SendingOccurrence (?so), threadHasOccurrence(?t, ?so), ReceivingOccurrence (?ro), threadHasOccurrence(?t, ?ro), EmailHeader (?eh), occurrenceHasEmailHeader(?ro, ?eh), IP (?i1), IP (?i2), SenderDevice (?sd), RecipientDevice (?rd), deviceHasId(?sd, ?i1), deviceHasId (?rd, ?i2), occurrenceResidesInDevice (?so, ?sd), occurrenceResidesInDevice (?ro, ?rd) → FeasibleEmail (?x)</i>
	An email <i>?x</i> is feasible to analyze when: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has a sequence <i>?s</i> associated by the relationship <i>emailHasSequence</i>, and there is a thread <i>?h</i> that relates to <i>?s</i> by <i>sequenceHasThread</i>, and in addition there are at least two occurrences, of which one is an <i>SendingOccurrence</i> and the other is an <i>ReceivingOccurrence</i> identified as <i>?so</i>, and <i>?ro</i>, which are associated with <i>?h</i> through the respective relationships <i>threadHasOccurrence</i>. - There is a <i>EmailHeader</i> associated with the <i>ReceivingOccurrence</i> by <i>occurrenceHasEmailHeader</i>. - There are two IP addresses identified as <i>?ip1</i> and <i>?ip2</i>, and two devices named <i>?sd</i>, and <i>?rd</i> that are instances of <i>SenderDevice</i> and <i>RecipientDevice</i> respectively, and the <i>deviceHasId</i> relationship associates the IP address instances with the indicated device instances, and finally, the <i>occurrenceResidesInDevice</i> relationship links each occurrence with the respective device. - Finally, the <i>Occurrence</i> and <i>Device</i> classes are linked through the relation <i>occurrenceResidesInDevice</i> with a cardinality one to one, this is so since, when circulating the email in the different servers used in the transmission, a single copy of it (or occurrence) remains on each server. The inverse relationship, called <i>deviceHasOccurrence</i>, is established between the <i>Device</i> class and the <i>Occurrence</i> class. 	
1.8	<i>Everything email have a unique Sequence of Occurrence</i>	<i>Email(?x), Sequence(?s1), emailHasSequence(?x, ?s1), Sequence(?s2), emailHasSequence (?x, ?s2) → SameAs (?s1, ?s2)</i>
	The uniqueness of <i>Sequence</i> with respect to email is expressed, indicating that for all email <i>?x</i> , if there are two sequences <i>?s1</i> and <i>?s2</i> that are related to <i>?x</i> by the relationship <i>emailHasSequence</i> , then <i>?s1</i> and <i>?s2</i> represent the same individual.	
ITEM	2	
CLASS	OCCURRENCE	
SUBCLASSES		
SUBITEM	Subclass Name	Description
2.1	<i>SendingOccurrence</i>	The first occurrence of email. It is always unique and is linked to the sender's device

2.2	<i>TransmissionOccurrence</i>	It is the intermediate occurrence, which is neither initial nor final, there must be at least one and is linked to the servers involved in the transmission process
2.3	<i>ReceivingOccurrence</i>	It is the last occurrence of the email and is linked to the recipient's device.
RELATIONS		
SUBITEM	Relationship Name	Description
2.4	<i>occurrenceBelongsToEmail</i>	Each occurrence is always linked to a single email through a one-to-one relationship. It is the inverse of the relation 1.3.
2.5	<i>occurrenceHasEmailAttachment</i>	If the email has an attachment, it relates to an occurrence according to the appropriate cardinality (none or several). It is the inverse of the 7.1 relation.
2.6	<i>occurrenceHasEmailSubject</i>	It links the occurrence to the email subject using a one-to-one relationship. It is the inverse of the 5.1 relation.
2.7	<i>occurrenceHasEmailHeader</i>	It links the occurrence to the email header using a one-to-one relationship. It is the inverse of the 4.1 relation.
2.8	<i>occurrenceHasEmailBody</i>	It links the occurrence to the email body using a one-to-one relationship. It is the inverse of the 6.1 relation.
2.9	<i>occurrenceTakesPlaceInDevice</i>	Indicates the recipient's device on which the occurrence resides. It is the inverse of the relation 8.5.
2.10	<i>occurrenceBelongsToThread</i>	Point out the Thread to which the occurrence corresponds, it will always be a one-to-one relationship. It is the inverse of the 12.2 relation.
2.11	<i>isPreviousTo</i>	Establishes the relationship of one occurrence to the next occurrence of the thread. It is the inverse of the relation 2.12
2.12	<i>occursAfter</i>	Establishes the relationship of one occurrence to the previous occurrence of the thread. It is the inverse of the relation 2.11.
AXIOMS		
SUBITEM	Axiom in natural language	SWRL expression
2.13	Everything Occurrence has a single Email Header	$Occurrence(?o), EmailHeader(?eh1), EmailHeader(?eh2), emailHeaderBelongsToOccurrence(?eh1, ?o), emailHeaderBelongsToOccurrence(?eh2, ?o) \rightarrow SameAs(?eh1, ?eh2)$
	It is established the uniqueness of <i>EmailHeader</i> with respect to <i>Occurrence</i> , indicating that for every occurrence <i>?o</i> , if there are two email headers called <i>?eh1</i> and <i>?eh2</i> that are related to <i>?o</i> by the relationship <i>emailHeaderBelongsToOccurrence</i> , then <i>?eh1</i> and <i>?eh2</i> must represent the same pitch.	
2.14	Everything Occurrence has a single Email Subject	$Occurrence(?o), EmailSubject(?es1), EmailSubject(?es2), emailSubjectBelongsToOccurrence(?es1, ?o), emailSubjectBelongsToOccurrence(?es2, ?o) \rightarrow SameAs(?es1, ?es2)$
	It is expressed the uniqueness of <i>EmailSubject</i> with respect to <i>Occurrence</i> , indicating that for every occurrence <i>?o</i> , if there are two email subjects <i>?es1</i> and <i>?es2</i> that are related to <i>?o</i> by the relationship <i>emailSubjectBelongsToOccurrence</i> , then <i>?es1</i> and <i>?es2</i> represent the same email subject.	
2.15	Everything Occurrence has a single Email Body	$Occurrence(?o), EmailBody(?eb1), EmailBody(?eb2), emailBodyBelongsToOccurrence(?eb1, ?o), emailBodyBelongsToOccurrence(?eb2, ?o) \rightarrow SameAs(?eb1, ?eb2)$
	It is expressed the uniqueness of <i>EmailBody</i> with respect to <i>Occurrence</i> , indicating that for every occurrence <i>?o</i> , if there are two instances of the <i>EmailBody</i> called <i>?eb1</i> and <i>?eb2</i> that are related to <i>?o</i> by the relationship <i>emailBodyBelongsToOccurrence</i> , then <i>?es1</i> and <i>?es2</i> represent the same email body.	
2.16	All Threads in an Email share the same Emission Occurrence	$Email(?x), Sequence(?s), emailHasSequence(?x, ?s), Thread(?h1), Thread(?h2), sequenceHasThread(?s, ?h1), sequenceHasThread(?s, ?h2), SendingOccurrence(?so1), SendingOccurrence(?so2), threadHasOccurrence(?h1, ?so1), threadHasOccurrence(?h2, ?so2) \rightarrow SameAs(?so1, ?so2)$
	For all email <i>?x</i> that has a sequence <i>?s</i> (expressing this link by the relationship <i>emailHasSequence</i>) and two threads identified as <i>?h1</i> and <i>?h2</i> , which are threads of that sequence <i>?s</i> (as indicated by the relation <i>sequenceHasThread</i> established thread between sequence and each thread), and there are also two emission occurrences identified as <i>?so1</i> and <i>?so2</i> which are linked respectively with the threads <i>?h1</i> and <i>?h2</i> by the relation <i>threadHasOccurrence</i> , then, both occurrences <i>?so1</i> and <i>?so2</i> represent the same occurrence.	

ITEM	3	
CLASS	ACCOUNT	
SUBCLASSES		
SUBITEM	Subclass Name	Description
3.1	SENDER_ACCOUNT	It identifies the account used to send the email. For each email it is always unique.
3.2	RECIPIENT_ACCOUNT	It identifies the account used to receive the email. They can be one or several.
RELATIONS		
SUBITEM	Relationship Name	Description
3.3	<i>senderAccountSendsEmail</i>	It indicates the account that acts as the email issuance account. It is the inverse of the relation 1.2
3.4	<i>senderAccountUsesSenderDevice</i>	It links the sender account to the sender's device. It is the inverse of the relation 8.8.

3.5	<i>recipientAccountReceivedEmail</i>	It identifies the accounts to which the email is sent, its cardinality is multiple at both ends of the relationship. It is the inverse of the relation 1.4.
3.6	<i>recipientAccountUsesRecipientDevice</i>	It links the receiving account to the recipient device. It is the inverse of the relation 8.6.
3.7	<i>accountLinkedToCaseFile</i>	It indicates the Case File linked to the email account under analysis. It is the inverse of the relation 13.1
3.8	<i>sendsFrom</i>	It indicates the sender's device on which the sender account resides. It is the inverse of the 10.5 relation.
3.9	<i>receivesIn</i>	It indicates the recipient's device on which the recipient account resides. It is the inverse of the 10.3 relation.
AXIOMS		
SUBITEM	Axiom in natural language	SWRL expression
3.10	<i>Everything account that acts as a sender uses a sender's device that runs an email client</i>	$SenderAccount(?sa), \quad SenderDevice(?sd), \quad EmailClient(?ec),$ $senderAccountUsesSenderDevice \quad (?sa, \quad ?sd),$ $senderDeviceHasEmailClient (?sd, ?ec) \rightarrow sendsFrom (?sa, ?ec)$
	For any account that intervenes as a transmitter <i>?sa</i> , if it is related to a sender's device <i>?sd</i> through the relationship <i>senderAccountUsesSenderDevice</i> , and the device <i>?sd</i> is related to an email client <i>?ec</i> through the relationship <i>senderDeviceHasEmailClient</i> , then, it is possible to infer that the account of the sender account <i>?sa</i> is linked to the email client <i>?ec</i> using the <i>sendsFrom</i> relation.	
3.11	<i>Everything account that acts as a receiver uses a recipient's device that runs an email client</i>	$RecipientAccount(?ra), \quad RecipientDevice \quad (?rd), \quad EmailClient \quad (?ec),$ $recipientAccountUsesRecipientDevice \quad (?ra, \quad ?rd),$ $RecipientDevice \quad HasEmailClient \quad (?rd, ?ec) \rightarrow receivesIn(?ra, ?ec)$
	For any account that acts as a receiver <i>?ra</i> , if it is related to a recipient's device <i>?rd</i> by the relationship <i>recipientAccountUsesRecipientDevice</i> , and the device <i>?rd</i> is related to an email client <i>?ec</i> by the relationship <i>RecipientDevice HasEmailClient</i> , then it is possible to infer that <i>?ra</i> is linked to <i>?ec</i> by relation <i>receivesIn</i> .	
3.12	<i>Everything Account that acts as a receiver has a single Thread of Occurrence</i>	$RecipientAccount (?ra), \quad Email(?x), \quad recipientAccountReceivedEmail (?ra,$ $?x), \quad Sequence(?s), \quad Thread(?h1), \quad Thread(?h2), \quad emailHasSequence (?x,$ $?s), \quad sequenceHasThread (?s, ?h1), \quad sequenceHasThread (?s, ?h2),$ $ReceivingOccurrence(?ro), \quad threadHasOccurrence (?h1, ?ro),$ $threadHasOccurrence (?h2, ?ro)$ $\rightarrow SameAs (?h1, ?h2)$
	For all email <i>?x</i> that is received by a recipient account <i>?ra</i> (expressing this link through the <i>recipientAccountReceivedEmail</i> relationship), it is true that if the email <i>?x</i> has a sequence <i>?s</i> (indicated by the relationship <i>emailHasSequence</i>), and there are two threads identified as <i>?h1</i> and <i>?h2</i> , which are threads of that sequence <i>?s</i> (as indicated by the relationship <i>sequenceHasThread</i> established between sequence and each thread), and in addition there is an receiving occurrence <i>?ro</i> to which the threads <i>?h1</i> and <i>?h2</i> are linked by the relationship <i>threadHasOccurrence</i> , then, <i>?h1</i> and <i>?h2</i> represent the same thread.	

ITEM	4	
CLASS	EMAIL_HEADER	
RELATIONS		
SUBITEM	Relationship Name	Description
4.1	<i>emailHeaderBelongsToOccurrence</i>	It indicates the occurrence to which the email header is linked in a one-to-many relationship. It is the inverse of the 2.7 relation.

ITEM	5	
CLASS	EMAIL_SUBJECT	
RELATIONS		
SUBITEM	Relationship Name	Description
5.1	<i>emailSubjectBelongsToOccurrence</i>	It indicates the occurrence to which the email subject is linked in a one-to-many relationship. It is the inverse of the relation 2.6.
5.2	<i>emailSubjectContainsKeyword</i>	It establishes the relationship between the email subject and the keyword that is used as the search parameter. It is an optional relationship. It is the inverse of the 14.4 relation.

ITEM	6	
CLASS	EMAIL_BODY	
RELATIONS		
SUBITEM	Relationship Name	Description
6.1	<i>emailBodyBelongsToOccurrence</i>	It points out the occurrence to which the email body is linked in a one-to-many relationship. It is the inverse of the relation 2.8.
6.2	<i>emailBodyContainsKeyword</i>	It establishes the relationship between the email body and the keyword that is used as the search parameter. It is an optional relationship. It is the inverse of the 14.2 relation.

ITEM	7	
CLASS	EMAIL_ATTACHMENT	
RELATIONS		
SUBITEM	Relationship Name	Description
7.1	<i>emailAttachmentBelongsToOccurrence</i>	When the email contains an attachment, this relationship signals the occurrence to which the attachment is linked in a one-to-many relationship. It is the inverse of the relation 2.5

7.2	<i>emailAttachmentContainsKeyword</i>	It establishes the relationship between the email attachment and the keyword that is used as the search parameter. It is an optional relationship. It is the inverse of the 14.3 relation.
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ITEM	8	
CLASS	DEVICE	
SUBCLASSES		
SUBITEM	Subclass Name	Description
8.1	SENDER_DEVICE	It identifies the device on which the sender account resides.
8.2	RECIPIENT_DEVICE	It identifies the device on which the recipient account resides.
8.3	SERVER	It identifies the device involved in the transmission process and is not the sending or receiving device.
RELATIONS		
SUBITEM	Relationship Name	Description
8.4	<i>deviceHasId</i>	It links each device with the corresponding identifier. It is the inverse of the 9.3 relation.
8.5	<i>deviceHasOccurrence</i>	It links the device to the occurrence it stores during the transmission process. It is the inverse of the relation 2.9.
8.6	<i>recipientDeviceIsUsedByRecipientAccount</i>	It links the receiving device to the receiving account resident on that device. It is the inverse relation of 3.6.
8.7	<i>recipientDeviceHasEmailClient</i>	It links the recipient's device to the email client installed on that device. It is the inverse relation of 10.4.
8.8	<i>senderDeviceIsUsedBySenderAccount</i>	It links the sender's device to the sender account resident on that device. It is the inverse relation of 3.4.
8.9	<i>senderDeviceHasEmailClient</i>	It links the sender's device to the email client installed on that device. It is the inverse relation of 10.6.

ITEM	9	
CLASS	DEVICE_IDENTIFICATION	
SUBCLASSES		
SUBITEM	Subclass Name	Description
9.1	HOSTNAME	It identifies the device by a domain name.
9.2	IP_ADDRESS	It identifies the device by an IP address.
RELATIONS		
SUBITEM	Relationship Name	Description
9.3	<i>idBelongsToDevice</i>	It indicates the identification that a device has. It is the inverse of the relation 8.4.

ITEM	10	
CLASS	EMAIL_CLIENT	
SUBCLASSES		
SUBITEM	Subclass Name	Description
10.1	LOCAL_EMAIL_CLIENT	It identifies the email client residing on the sending or receiving device.
10.2	REMOTE_EMAIL_CLIENT	It identifies the email client that is accessed remotely via the web
RELATIONS		
SUBITEM	Relationship Name	Description
10.3	<i>emailClientSupportsRecipientAccount</i>	It links the email client to the recipient account. It is the inverse relation of 3.9.
10.4	<i>emailClientIsRunByRecipientDevice</i>	It links the mail client with the recipient's device. It is the inverse ratio of 8.7.
10.5	<i>emailClientSupportsSenderAccount</i>	It links the email client to the sender account. It is the inverse relation of 3.8.
10.6	<i>emailClientIsRunBySenderDevice</i>	It links the mail client with the sender's device. It is the inverse ratio of 8.9.

ITEM	11	
CLASS	SEQUENCE	
RELATIONS		
SUBITEM	Relationship Name	Description
11.1	<i>sequenceBelongsToEmail</i>	It links the sequence corresponding to the email under analysis. It is the inverse relation of 1.5.
11.2	<i>sequenceHasThread</i>	It links the sequence to the corresponding threads. The relation can be from 1 to several . It is the inverse relation of 12.1.

ITEM	12	
CLASS	THREAD	
RELATIONS		
SUBITEM	Relationship Name	Description
12.1	<i>threadBelongsToSequence</i>	It links each thread to the corresponding sequence. It's a one-to-one relationship. It is the inverse relation of 11.2.

12.2	<i>threadHasOccurrence</i>	It links the occurrences that correspond to a thread. It is the inverse relation of 2.10.
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ITEM	13	
CLASS	CASE_FILE	
RELATIONS		
SUBITEM	Relationship Name	Description
13.1	<i>caseFileLinkAccount</i>	It links the Case File to the account being analyzed. It is the inverse relation of 3.7.
13.2	<i>caseFileContainsKeyword</i>	It links the Case File to the search keyword. It can be a multiple relationship. It is the inverse relation of 14.1.

ITEM	14	
CLASS	KEYWORD	
RELATIONS		
SUBITEM	Relationship Name	Description
14.1	<i>keywordIsInCaseFile</i>	It links the search keyword to the Case File. It can be a multiple relationship. It is the inverse relation of 13.2.
14.2	<i>keywordIsInBodyEmail</i>	It links the search keyword to the body email. It can be a multiple relationship. It is the inverse relation of 6.2.
14.3	<i>keywordIsInEmailAttachment</i>	It links the search keyword to the attachment email. It can be a multiple relationship. It is the inverse relation of 7.2.
14.4	<i>keywordIsInSubjectEmail</i>	It links the search keyword to the email subject. It can be a multiple relationship. It is the inverse relation of 5.2.